

ISic0822

I.Sicily inscription 0822

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

dedication;

building

Material

limestone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Temple of Apollo, Ortygia

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Tempio di Apollo

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Κλεομ[]ἔς [] ἐποίεσε τόπέλῶνι [] ἡο Κνιδ,ιδά [] ΚΕ[]ΕΣ []ΥΛΕΙΑ [] κα[]λά[]
φέργα

Apparatus

Text after Marconi 2007, 42-47

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492448

EDCS 39101970

PHI 140290

PHI 329568

PHI 329694

PHI 330110

PHI 333377
PHI 333763
PHI 333764

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